

A Systematic Literature Review of Flexibility and Organizational Culture Essential for SMEs in a Competitive Marketplace

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ABSTRACT: Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in driving the global economy, but are often faced with major challenges in responding to rapid market changes. Limited resources, volatile business conditions and high levels of competition require SMEs to develop effective adaptive strategies. Operational flexibility is a key factor that enables SMEs to adjust to these changes. However, previous research shows that there is a gap in understanding the application of operational flexibility in improving business efficiency. Furthermore, there are not many in-depth studies that address how adaptive organizational culture interacts with operational flexibility to build competitive advantage, especially for SMEs in emerging markets. This study aims to answer two key questions: How does operational flexibility support SMEs in dealing with market changes and improving business efficiency? How does the synergy between adaptive organizational culture and operational flexibility contribute to creating competitive advantage for SMEs? Using the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method, this study analyzed 18 primary sources selected based on specific quality and relevance criteria. The study results show that operational flexibility helps SMEs respond more quickly to market changes through optimizing resource use and strategic decision-making. It also supports improved operational efficiency by facilitating the adoption of innovative technologies and the adjustment of business strategies to market needs. Moreover, the interaction between operational flexibility and an adaptive organizational culture - enriched by values such as collaboration, innovation and learning - plays a role in building dynamic capabilities that strengthen SMEs' competitiveness. This study makes a significant contribution to the literature by expanding the understanding of the role of operational flexibility and adaptive culture as strategic elements in improving SME performance. The main recommendation of this study emphasizes the importance of integrating operational flexibility with the development of an adaptive organizational culture as a holistic approach to strengthen the competitiveness of SMEs amid increasingly fierce market competition.

KEYWORDS: SMEs, operational flexibility, adaptive organizational culture, dynamic capabilities, business efficiency, competitive advantage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a very important role in driving economic growth in various countries, including on a global scale. SMEs are not only the main driver in creating jobs, but also contribute significantly to the development of local innovation and strengthening the competitiveness of the national economy. However, despite their strategic role, SMEs are faced with complex challenges, especially when it comes to adapting to changing market dynamics. Some of the key challenges that SMEs often face include limited resources, such as access to capital, technology, and expertise, as well as the volatility of the business environment influenced by market fluctuations, regulatory changes, or competitive pressures from larger companies (Chan et al., 2019). To remain competitive, operational flexibility is an essential element that enables SMEs to respond to market changes quickly and efficiently, while an adaptive organizational culture can provide the foundation for this flexibility to flourish. The interaction between these two elements is considered a key factor for creating sustainable competitive advantage. Therefore, this study aims to explore how operational flexibility helps SMEs adapt to market dynamics and improve business efficiency, and how an adaptive organizational culture strengthens such flexibility. Operational flexibility in the context of these challenges, becomes a core capability that is very important for SMEs. Operational flexibility provides opportunities for SMEs to respond to market changes quickly and efficiently, for example by optimally utilizing available resources and making adjustments to ongoing business strategies or processes. The ability to make quick and appropriate decisions is also an integral part of this flexibility, which in turn supports improved operational efficiency and strengthens the competitiveness of SMEs in a competitive market (Azeem et al., 2021) (Al Azzani et al., 2024). In addition to operational flexibility, an adaptive organizational culture also plays a crucial role in helping SMEs cope with change. An organizational culture characterized by values such as innovation, collaboration, and learning provides a strong foundation for operational flexibility to thrive. Through the adoption of this culture, SMEs can build dynamic capabilities that enable them to effectively manage change, both in facing challenges and in capitalizing on new opportunities that arise in the market. This not only helps SMEs stay relevant, but also creates a competitive advantage in the long run (Liu, 2021) (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023). This systematic literature review was

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designed to evaluate the current state of knowledge regarding the importance of Flexibility and Organizational Culture for SMEs in Competitive Markets. With reference to The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA), this study reviewed 18 articles as of December 7, 2024 with a literature search of the Scopus database. This review examines how organizational culture and flexibility can help SMEs improve their competitiveness by: Creating strong market capabilities, Creating competitive advantage, Maintaining good customer relations, Increasing employee loyalty, Increasing corporate trust and reputation. A good organizational culture in MSMEs can be formed with: Good leadership, Clear vision and mission of the company, Togetherness between business owners and employees, Flexibility in running the business.

Some ways to maintain a positive organizational culture are:

1. Creating a positive work climate
2. Valuing the contribution of each member
3. Building trust and mutual understanding
4. Being a positive role model
5. Providing training and development
6. Building partnerships and cooperation

Systematic Literature Review (SLR) offers a more rigorous and structured approach to analyzing existing literature (E. C. L. Yanet al., 2017a). This method enables the systematic identification, evaluation, and synthesis of research evidence, reduces bias, and results in a more comprehensive understanding of how flexibility and organizational culture contribute to SME success. Through SLR, this research aims to answer the fundamental question: How does the interaction between organizational flexibility and corporate culture affect the competitiveness of SMEs in dynamic markets?

The main objectives of this SLR are to:

1. Identify and synthesize empirical evidence on the relationship between organizational flexibility, corporate culture, and SME performance.
2. Analyze best practices in building flexibility and a culture that supports competitive advantage
3. Develop a conceptual framework that can assist SMEs in optimizing their organizational flexibility and culture

The significance of this research lies in its contribution to both theory and practice. Theoretically, this SLR will fill the gap in our understanding of how soft (culture) and hard (flexibility) organizational factors interact in the context of SMEs. Practically, the findings from this study will provide guidance for SME owners and managers in developing more adaptive and culturally strong organizations, as well as assist policy makers in designing more effective support programs for the SME sector. SLR emphasizes a systematic process of literature search, abstraction, and synthesis (E. C. L. Yang et al., 2017b). Systematic reviews can include knowledge generated through qualitative and quantitative approaches. Practical, objective, and reliable discussions and findings are provided by SLR. SLR presents a great opportunity for academics and practitioners to apply existing knowledge for policy-making and future research (Pahlevan-Sharif et al., 2019). This methodology is very effective in planning field coverage. In this study, five steps of SLR were conducted, which were adapted from The Benefits of Publishing Systematic Quantitative Literature Reviews for PhD Candidates and Other Early-Career Researchers.Pdf, n.d.) (Marek et al., 2009). Step 1 contains the purpose of the review is determined, and research questions are formulated, in step 2 contains the review protocol is formulated by identifying search terms and databases in addition to establishing literature selection criteria. Then, in step 3 contains the identified database of relevant literature and then selected based on predetermined criteria. Step 4 contains all relevant information extracted and summarized in tabular form, finally step 5 contains the content analysis performed (E. C. L. Yang et al., 2017b) (Haddaway et al., 2022) All steps are shown in Figure 1.

METHODOLOGY

This SLR explores how Flexibility and Organizational Culture Matter for SMEs in Competitive Markets" has been examined earlier

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in this study. topic, context, sample, methods, findings, and future research. The SLR began by setting the objectives of the review as described in detail in the previous section. This literature review answers the following research question: How Flexibility and Organizational Culture Matter for SMEs in Competitive Markets"

1. Literature Review Protocol

The review protocol contains the database, search terms, and literature selection criteria. The following word scheme was used to obtain research exploring Flexibility and Organizational Culture Important for SMEs in Competitive Markets" ("Small businesses" OR "SMEs" OR "small and medium enterprises" OR "entrepreneurship" OR "micro businesses") AND ("competitive market" OR "market changes" OR "market competition" OR "market environment") AND ("Flexibility" OR "Agility" OR "Adaptability" OR "Resilience"). To achieve multidisciplinary coverage and relevant literature was searched in the scopus database of the most significant small and medium enterprises. Although previous systematic reviews mostly considered two to three databases (E. C. L. Yang et al., 2017b), the review of this study is only from the main data, namely Scopus. The search data in this study included research titles, keywords, abstracts, or texts, and published in English academic journals within the time span of 2019 to 2024. The selection of English is due to the main language in international academic publishing (E. C. L. Yang et al., 2017b), so in this research review is the main reason for selecting peer-reviewed academic journals published in English and covering a period of 5 years.

2. Literature Screening

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) was used for the literature screening that formed the basis of this research review (Haddaway et al., 2022). The PRISMA conducted in this study (Haddaway et al., 2022) outlines the steps to be followed to conduct the review and generate reliable data. The PRISMA methodology will contribute to a clearer understanding of the conduct, quality and rigor of systematic reviews. The rationale behind the choice of PRISMA (Marek et al., 2009) over other existing protocols lies in the recognition of its comprehensiveness, its use in several disciplines worldwide, and its potential to improve consistency across reviews (Pahlevan-Sharif et al., 2019). In addition, to select articles using the Parsifal tool makes it easier to select considering there are several articles that are not open access.

Formulation of RQ Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in the global economy, particularly as job creators, drivers of innovation, and drivers of local economic growth. Nonetheless, SMEs often face significant challenges in adapting to market dynamics, such as the uncertainty of the business environment, limited resources, and pressure from larger companies. In this context, operational flexibility is one of the key factors that enable SMEs to respond quickly to market changes and improve business efficiency. In addition, an adaptive organizational culture, with values such as innovation, collaboration, and learning, plays an important role in strengthening SMEs' capabilities to effectively manage change.

Systematic Searching Strategy

This study uses a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach to identify, analyze, and synthesize research related to how operational flexibility helps SMEs adapt to market dynamics and improve business efficiency. The SLR approach was chosen as it provides a clear structure for the literature search, ensuring that the process is transparent, replicable and free from selection bias (Pahlevan-Sharif et al., 2019). The systematic search strategy was conducted through the following steps:

1. Database Identification
2. Keywords and Search Strings
3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria
4. Proses Screening
5. Data Extraction
6. Analysis and Synthesis
7. Validation and Quality Evaluation
8. Process Documentation
9. Result / Finding

This research identifies important findings related to operational flexibility and its role in helping SMEs adapt to market dynamics and improve business efficiency. Operational flexibility enables SMEs to respond quickly to market changes through efficient resource management, both internal and external, and responsive strategic decision-making. This research underscores that operational flexibility not only improves business efficiency, but also strengthens the competitiveness of SMEs through interaction with an adaptive organizational culture. The findings offer practical insights for decision-makers in SMEs to integrate operational flexibility with cultural values that support innovation and collaboration to sustain their business in a changing market environment. In detail, the main findings can be summarized as follows:

1. Operational Flexibility as Key to Market Adaptation and Adaptation to Market Dynamics
2. Efficiency Improvement Through Resource Optimization
3. Strategic Implications of Operational Flexibility for SME Competitiveness
4. The Interaction Between Flexibility and Innovation
5. Dynamic Capabilities and Competitive Advantage
6. Challenges and Barriers in Implementing Operational Flexibility
7. Practical Recommendations

The findings of this study confirm that operational flexibility is a key element that enables SMEs to adapt to market dynamics,

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improve business efficiency, and strengthen their competitiveness. Through the ability to adjust business processes, maximize resource use, and respond quickly to market changes, operational flexibility helps SMEs remain relevant and competitive in a changing business environment. However, the implementation of this flexibility requires strategic support, both from within the organization and from the external environment, to ensure its success across different sectors and markets. Overall, this study underscores that operational flexibility not only improves business efficiency, but also strengthens SMEs' competitiveness through the interaction with an adaptive organizational culture. The findings offer practical insights for decision-makers in SMEs to integrate operational flexibility with cultural values that support innovation and collaboration to sustain their business in a changing market environment.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

All Article Analysis Table

No	Author	Year	Title	Description	Results
1	Muhammad Azeem *, Munir Ahmed, Sajid Haider, Muhammad Sajjad	2021	Expanding competitive advantage through organizational culture,	Investigating the Relationship of organizational culture, knowledge sharing, innovation	Organizational culture, knowledge sharing, and innovation have a positive effect
2	I Wayan Edi Arsawan 1,*, Ni Kadek Dessy Hariyanti 1 , I Made Ari Dwi Suta	2022	Developing Organizational Agility in SMEs: An Investigation	Examine the relationship between social capital, knowledge creation collaboration, innovation, and organizational agility, and the moderating role of strategic flexibility.	Social capital influences knowledge creation collaboration, innovation, and organizational agility, but knowledge creation collaboration has no impact on agility. Strategic flexibility does not moderate the relationship between innovation and agility.
3	Calvin M.L. Chan1 Say Yen Teoh2 Adrian Yeow1 Gary Pan3	2019	Agility in responding to Disruptive digital innovation: Case study of an SME	Examine how SMEs achieve agility in response to disruptive digital innovations and develop an agility framework.	SMEs achieve agility through mitigating organizational rigidity with boundary openness, developing innovative capabilities with organizational adaptability, and balancing ambidexterity to manage resource limitations.
4	Hsian-Ming Liu*	2021	Effect of partnership quality on SMEs success: Mediating role of coordination capability and organisational agility	Examine the effect of partnership quality (PQ) on organizational performance (FP) through coordination ability (CC) and organizational agility (OA) in SMEs.	Partnership quality (PQ) improves organizational performance (FP) through coordination ability (CC) and organizational agility (OA). SMEs need to maintain PQ to overcome resource limitations and create a competitive advantage in a dynamic market.
5	Paolo Boccadelli1* and Mats G. Magnusson2	2006	Dynamic Capabilities in Early-Phase Entrepreneurship	Investigate how start-ups match resources to market needs and the role of resource flexibility in the process.	Start-ups that change market focus tend to survive longer without the need to change technological resources. Early dynamic capabilities are more of a bricolage, recombining existing resources to match market demand. Resource flexibility and the role of the entrepreneur need to be included in the dynamic capability framework.
6	Yang 1,2, Shuhe Shi 1,2,*, and Jingjing Wu 3	2022	Digital Financial Inclusion to Corporation Value: The Mediating Effect of	Explores the impact of digital financial inclusion on SME firm value, as well as the moderating role of	Digital financial inclusion enhances exploitation innovation, with ambidextrous innovation as a partial intermediary. Financial

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			Ambidextrous Innovation	financial flexibility, Corporate social responsibility, and market competition in ambidextrous innovation.	flexibility strengthens this relationship, while corporate social responsibility has a short-term negative impact but supports long-term firm value. Product market competition strengthens the relationship between digital financial inclusion and exploitation innovation.
7	Andrea Cardoni 1,* Filippo Zanin 2, Giulio Corazza 2 and Alessio Paradisi 1	2020	Knowledge Management and Performance Measurement Systems for SMEs' Economic Sustainability	Explore the relationship between knowledge management (KM), performance measurement systems (PMS), and economic sustainability of SMEs in knowledge-based sectors.	An exploratory KM approach positively influences SMEs' economic sustainability, and Consistent PMS implementation strengthens this relationship. This research advises SMEs to design a coherent KM approach and implement appropriate PMS to support economic sustainability.
8	Teng Ma, Ya Liu * and Rongyan Jia	2023	Multiple Driving Paths of High-Tech SME Resilience from a "Resource– Capability– Environment" Perspective: An fsQCA Approach	Analyze the pathways driving the organizational resilience of high-tech-based SMEs with a resource, capability, and environment approach.	Three pathways driving high resilience were found: resource-capability, resource- capability-environment, and resource-environment. This research reveals that the organizational resilience of high-tech SMEs is influenced by the complex interaction of various factors and provides insights for managers in improving resilience and sustainability.
9	Hamed Ali Al Azzani1 , Normal Mat Jusoh1, and Aamir Abbas2	2024	Market and Supply Chain Orientation; Dynamic Capabilities Leading to Innovation and Operational Capabilities	Analyzing the effect of supply chain and market orientation on SME performance in Oman, with innovation and operational capabilities mediation and strategic flexibility moderation.	Market and supply chain orientation enhance SMEs' innovation capabilities, operations, and performance. These capabilities mediate the relationship between market/supply chain orientation and SME performance, but strategic flexibility does not moderate the effect of innovation capabilities.
10	Aqueeb Sohail Shaik, Monika Jain, Aparna Mendiratta, Ghadah Alarifi and Elisa Arrigo	2023	Role of strategic knowledge management practices in enhancing strategic perspectives of an organization to improve entrepreneurial performance	This study investigates the impact of strategic knowledge management (SKM) practices and organizational change capacity (OCC) on strategic thinking, strategic orientation, and entrepreneurial performance in SMEs.	The findings show that investments in SKM and OCC help SMEs adapt to market changes, develop effective strategies and improve entrepreneurial performance. The research emphasizes the importance of SKM and OCC in creating a culture of innovation and agility, and provides recommendations for policies to support SMEs in implementing these two practices.

The Importance of Operational Flexibility in a Changing Business Environment

Operational flexibility allows SMEs to adapt their strategies to changing market conditions quickly. In the context of SMEs, which often have limited resources, this flexibility helps them make optimal use of existing resources to respond to changes without incurring significant additional costs (Al Azzani et al., 2024) (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023). The ability to adapt to changing customer needs or market trends provides SMEs with a significant competitive advantage, especially in sectors that

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rely heavily on innovation and agility (Y. Yang et al., 2022) (Chan et al., 2019) (Cardoni et al., 2020). For example, when market demand shifts due to trends or changes in customer preferences, operational flexibility allows SMEs to shift their focus from less desirable products to products with higher market potential. With this approach, SMEs not only avoid financial losses, but can also maintain their relevance in the market (Cardoni et al., 2020) (Shaik et al., 2024).

Operational Flexibility as a Response to Market Dynamics

In the face of market dynamics, operational flexibility helps SMEs to stay relevant by ensuring they can adapt quickly to external changes. Research shows that SMEs with higher flexibility have a greater chance of surviving in a competitive market (Sánchez-Báez et al., 2020) (Al Azzani et al., 2024). For example, when customer preferences change, operational flexibility allows SMEs to develop new products or adapt their services to meet market needs (Chan et al., 2019) (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023).

Improving Business Efficiency through Operational Flexibility

Business efficiency is one of the key outcomes of operational flexibility. With the ability to manage resources efficiently, SMEs can reduce waste, increase productivity, and optimize the use of their assets (Malewska et al., 2024) (Ma et al., 2023). This not only helps in reducing costs but also increases profit margins, which is crucial for business sustainability (Xia et al., 2024) (Liu, 2021).

Challenges in Implementing Operational Flexibility

Many SMEs do not have the capacity to adopt advanced technologies or recruit skilled workers to support their operational flexibility (Chan et al., 2019) (Samuel Omokhafa Yusuf et al., 2024).

In addition, the lack of awareness about the importance of operational flexibility is also a barrier. Some SMEs may not be aware of the potential benefits they can gain from this flexibility, and are therefore reluctant to invest time and resources in developing it (Cardoni et al., 2020) (Azeem et al., 2021). Therefore, broader education and training are needed to increase understanding of the importance of operational flexibility among SMEs.

Practical Implications and Recommendations

1. Integrating Digital Technology
2. Developing Adaptive Processes
3. Improving Human Resources Competence

The Role of Operational Flexibility in Adapting to Market Dynamics

Operational flexibility provides a framework that allows companies to identify changes in the market, both opportunities and threats, and take quick steps to adjust their operations. For example, SMEs that implement operational flexibility can quickly adapt their production lines to meet changing customer preferences, such as increased demand for environmentally friendly products (Xia et al., 2024).

Optimizing Resources through Operational Flexibility

Operational flexibility provides a solution by enabling more efficient resource management. For example, SMEs can reallocate their resources based on strategic priorities, such as shifting labor to more urgent projects or optimizing the use of existing technology to increase productivity (Arsawan et al., 2022).

Improving Business Efficiency through Operational Flexibility

Business efficiency is one of the main positive impacts of implementing operational flexibility in SMEs. With the ability to adjust their business processes quickly and effectively, SMEs can reduce operational costs while maintaining the quality of their products or services. For example, SMEs operating in the manufacturing sector can use operational flexibility to reduce production downtime by quickly adjusting production schedules based on raw material availability or changes in market demand (E. C. L. Yang et al., 2017a).

Competitive Advantage Provided by Operational Flexibility

Operational flexibility not only helps SMEs in facing market challenges, but also provides significant competitive advantage. By being able to respond to market changes faster than their competitors, SMEs can build a reputation as responsive and innovative companies. This gives them an advantage in attracting and retaining customers, which is a critical asset in a competitive market (Gaganis et al., 2019).

Literature Gaps and Suggestions for Further Research

Although the benefits of operational flexibility have been widely identified, there are gaps in the literature that require further attention. Most previous studies tend to explore operational flexibility as a broad concept without delving deeper into its specific dimensions, such as flexibility in organizational structure, business processes, or technology use (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023). Future research is recommended to explore how these dimensions individually contribute to SME performance.

Implications of the Study

This study shows that operational flexibility enables more efficient resource management, rapid strategic decision-making, and implementation of relevant innovations, thereby enhancing SME business efficiency (Chan et al., 2019) (Azeem et al., 2021) (Shaik et al., 2024). In addition, this study strengthens the argument that adaptive organizational culture, through values such as collaboration, innovation, and learning, plays a vital role in strengthening the dynamic capabilities needed to create sustainable competitive advantage (Liu, 2021) (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023).

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From a practical perspective, these findings provide recommendations for SME leaders to integrate operational flexibility with an adaptive organizational culture strategy. Implementing values such as innovation, cross-functional collaboration, and calculated risk-taking can strengthen SME competitiveness in a dynamic market (Chan et al., 2019) (Liu, 2021) (Al Azzani et al., 2024). In addition, the use of digital technology and the development of dynamic capabilities enable SMEs to respond to market changes more effectively, take advantage of opportunities, and manage challenges (Al Azzani et al., 2024)(Xia et al., 2024). Policy implications can also be drawn from this study. Policymakers in the SME sector can support training and mentoring programs that focus on developing operational flexibility and adaptive organizational culture. For example, providing access to digital technologies and learning platforms can help SMEs develop the capabilities needed to compete in the global market (Shaik et al., 2024). Thus, this study not only contributes to the academic literature but also offers relevant practical insights for decision-makers and policymakers. Well-designed strategies based on operational flexibility and adaptive organizational culture can be the foundation for SMEs to remain competitive and sustainable in the changing market.

Research Gaps

There are several gaps that need to be filled for a more comprehensive understanding of the interaction of the two elements.

1. Missing Elements in the Literature

Most studies have focused more on the individual effects of operational flexibility or organizational culture on SME business performance, without exploring in depth how these two elements interact to create competitive advantage. For example, many studies discuss flexibility as a tool to cope with market dynamics but rarely link it directly to organizational culture transformation (Chan et al., 2019)(Azeem et al., 2021).

2. Key Unanswered Questions

How operational flexibility can be aligned with adaptive organizational culture elements in various market contexts remains incompletely answered. Research also lacks an explanation of how certain cultural values, such as cross-functional collaboration and risk-taking, can support the implementation of operational flexibility (Liu, 2021)(Onngam &, 2023).

3. Unaddressed Issues

Most existing studies focus on large firms or SMEs in developed countries, while the context of emerging markets with different challenging characteristics is often neglected. In this context, the application of operational flexibility and adaptive organizational culture in SMEs in developing countries requires further exploration (Shaik et al., 2024)(Samuel Omokhafa Yusuf et al., 2024).

4. Insufficient Information

There is a lack of empirical data supporting the relationship between operational flexibility and business efficiency, especially in the management of more specific resources such as digital technology and business model innovation. This limits the ability to draw stronger conclusions regarding the effectiveness of flexibility strategies (Azeem et al., 2021) (Xia et al., 2024).

5. Practical, Conceptual, and Methodological Issues

The methodologies used in previous literature are often generalist without considering sector variability, SME size, or organizational culture characteristics. More specific research approaches are needed to identify strategies that are relevant to SMEs across industries (Liu, 2021) (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023). Thus, this study seeks to fill this gap through an in-depth exploration of the interaction between operational flexibility and adaptive organizational culture, particularly in the context of SMEs in emerging markets. The results are expected to provide significant theoretical and practical contributions.

CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms that operational flexibility is a key element for SMEs to face the ever-changing market dynamics. This flexibility allows SMEs to respond quickly to market changes through efficient resource management and the implementation of relevant innovations. This not only improves business efficiency but also helps SMEs maintain their competitiveness in a competitive business environment (Azeem et al., 2021)(Chan et al., 2019)(Al Azzani et al., 2024)(Shaik et al., 2024). Strategic agility supported by innovation capabilities and digital technology is an important factor in supporting operational flexibility, enabling SMEs to create sustainable added value (Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023)(Xia et al., 2024). The interaction between adaptive organizational culture and operational flexibility has also been shown to create competitive advantages for SMEs. Organizational culture that supports innovation, collaboration, and learning strengthens SMEs' adaptability, enabling them to capitalize on opportunities and manage market challenges more effectively (Chan et al., 2019)(Onngam & Charoensukmongkol, 2023)(Samuel Omokhafa Yusuf et al., 2024). Values such as risk-taking and customer orientation play a significant role in strengthening SMEs' dynamic capabilities, making them better equipped to proactively address changes in the business environment (Sánchez-Báez et al., 2020)(Gaganis et al., 2019). Overall, this study makes an important contribution to the literature by linking operational flexibility, adaptive organizational culture, and competitive advantage in the context of SMEs, especially in emerging markets. From a practical perspective, this study offers insights for SME leaders and policy makers to integrate operational flexibility strategies with the development of adaptive organizational culture, to ensure sustainability and competitiveness in the global market.

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